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Strengthening the Implementation of Health in All Policies (HiAP) Approach at National and EU-level: The JA PreventNCD Project. A Protocol for the Collection of Written Data in Task 9.1.1.

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JA PreventNCD

This work is carried out in Joint Action project focusing on reduction of Europe's cancer and NCD burden through coordinated strategies on health determinants. <https://preventncd.eu/>

While JA PreventNCD has altogether 10 Work Packages, this work is being done under Work Package 9 which focuses on Health in All Policies. The main aim of this work package is to strengthen the implementation of Health in All Policies (HiAP) across different governance levels, focusing particularly on key risk factors and determinants to prevent cancer and other non-communicable diseases (NCDs). This involves: (i) improving our understanding of the current systems, processes and tools for HiAP, (ii) identifying opportunities and challenges with implementing HiAP, (iii) assessing the state of art in monitoring and evaluating policy implementation, and (iv) providing suggestions to strengthen HiAP implementation and engaging in discussions at both national and EU level.

Short task description

This task aims at understanding how HiAP is currently implemented and what are the opportunities and challenges of implementing it in various countries at national levels as well as at the EU level. To be able to answer these questions the task will not only study the administrative branch of governance but broadens the scope to legislative branch as well. Furthermore, we aim at exploring not only how HiAP is implemented regarding nationally implemented policies, but also how HiAP is practiced for preparing national stands for proposals arriving from the EU.

The primary objective of this task is to strengthen HiAP implementation by providing an updated understanding of current practices, including identification of opportunities and challenges in HiAP implementation at national levels in the participating countries and at EU level, and providing recommendations for improved implementation.

Analytical focus

The task will analyze implementation of HiAP approach across Europe and focus on legislative framework, structures, processes, tools and practices, resources.

Participants

Austria (GÖG), Bulgaria (NCPHA), Estonia (TAI), Finland (CSF), Germany (RKI, BzGA) Iceland (DOHI), Italy (UNITO), Norway (HDIRI), Portugal (ISPUP). Observers: France (RfVS), Slovenia (NIJZ)

The purpose of data collection

The collected documentary material will form the core data (together with the semi-structured interviews) for national draft reports and for the task report (minimum standards for comparability) and for scientific articles. Thorough analysis of the documentary material will also prepare us better for the interviews.

Timeline

In this task we have an interest in current practices, but we also try to track possible changes in policies. Current is defined as the last 6 years; therefore, we focus on documents produced in 2019-2024, but if there are significant changes in more distant history that are important to understand the present, those documents can be included. In terms of legislative framework, we are focusing on existing legislation (therefore the aforementioned timeline does not apply to laws: they can be older).

Guidelines for data collection

Collect all the relevant data from your country based on the framework presented below. Build a list of all the data, including exact bibliographical information of the documents (i.e., author/s, name of the document, year of publication), links to the virtual documents as well as dates of accessing them. Collect a library of virtual documents (i.e. save them to your computer) and copies of the printed documents. Make also sure that as soon as you find the document, you locate it straight away to the right section (1.-8.) of the protocol, in other words keep track of which section (e.g., legislation, structure etc.) and category it belongs. This will be useful when analyzing the data. If you do not find any data on some issues, please contact the Ministry of Health or other relevant instances and confirm the situation from them. If nothing is found, that must be notified too. If you need help in searching for the documents, use the Document Collection Guide to get started.

DOCUMENTS TO BE COLLECTED

(1) Legislative framework (Constitution, degree laws, statutes etc.)

What are the laws enforcing or enabling HiAP? They can be the health sector initiated or initiated by another sector.

Examples: law concerning obligations to establish intersectoral public health committee, law concerning obligations to consider health impacts with other policies, law concerning obligations to prepare national intersectoral health reports

On legislation please consider:

- a) Public health and health systems -related legislation related to public health, disease prevention, health promotion, health protection and health services functions
- b) General obligations for public policymaking with legal or legislative requirements for intersectoral consultations, impact assessments, policy coherence, or general requirements related to sustainability applying to all public policies. We are interested in particular on such general legislative obligations that have relevance to health and health equity.
- c) Constitutional obligations relevant to public health or inclusion of human rights or social rights obligations (i.e. health as a social or human right) to national legislation.
- d) Legislation that guides the responsibilities and duties of subnational actors on the aspects (a.-b.). (For subtask 9.1.2.)

(2) Structures

Structures can be located in the prime minister's cabinet office, in the council of state between ministers and their experts, in the administration involving various ministries, and in the parliament, for ex. parliamentary committees looking at health intersectorally.

Structures in administration:

- Are there intersectoral committees, advisory boards or major working groups on public health, nutrition, or physical activity? How are these different bodies called?
- Are there intersectoral committees, advisory boards or major working groups which focus on other general questions, such as poverty, housing, trade & consumer issues, transport & urban planning, or sustainability, to which health sector participates? How are these different bodies called?

Structures in parliaments:

- Is there a health committee in parliament or are health-related questions included under another committee? How are these different bodies called?

As many national policies are influenced by EU-level policies, it is important to know how member states form their national stands on EU-policy proposals.

- Is there a description available on how national stands for EU policy proposals are formed within the administrative branch and within the parliamentary structures?
- Is there an intersectoral body, process, or other type of system for forming the national stands on EU-level policy proposals? If so, is health represented?
- What are the documents (laws, decisions etc.) establishing that system?
- What is the role of health attaché (EU) and from whom does the health attaché receive directions?

In conclusion, please consider:

- Documents of main bodies (committees, boards, councils etc.) to enable intersectoral work for health on national level in administration and in the parliament and collect documentation on their name, establishment, mandate, and participating bodies.
- Documents of main bodies related to formulating national stands on EU-level policy proposals and collecting documentation on their name, establishment, mandate, and participating bodies.

(3) Processes (tick the boxes)

Can refer to processes or procedures, such as required co-operation between sectors, request for comments on certain proposals or decisions.

What kind of processes and procedures in addition to the legal framework exist for health problems needing intersectoral action?

Questions to find examples of processes	Yes	No	I don't know	What material found?
Is there a practice of asking for statements from other sectors and stakeholders (e.g. environment, education, agriculture, finance, trade) on policy proposals? If yes, is this practice based on law?				
Do you have wider cross-sectoral policy formulation activities on sustainability or equity? If yes, is health sectors part of these processes?				

Try to find the related documents on the above processes, if you do not find them, return to this in the interviews.

(4) Tools and practices

Practice can refer to, for example knowledge practices, communication practices, evaluation practices, work practices. Tools refer here to instruments to evaluate policies or to engage the public and the stakeholders (incl. academia and professional associations and private sector) in policymaking. Tools often come in the form of manuals, guidelines, or protocols, which are all intended to guide how to use them.

- Is there a manual or guidance for implementation of HIAP? If yes, find the document.
- Are there national health related gatherings or whole-of-society meetings? Name them and describe the purpose shortly.
- Is there documentation on participative practices engaging citizens which focus on health, such as health assemblies, citizen juries or public consultations and engagement? What are they? Find out documentation on these.
- Are there mandatory consultation requirements for health impact assessment, equity impact assessment or human impact assessment which could apply to health? Find out documents on such processes (health initiated, others, administrative, parliamentary, EU directed)

Examples: different measurement activities, tools such as health lens analysis, health equity lens analysis, gender lens analysis, HIA, HEIA etc.

(5) Resources

Resources refer to financial and human resources, institutional resources, knowledge related resources.

Examples: Resources for relevant data, its analyses and for informed decision-making, joint budgeting across administrative sectors

- Is there education in your country on a) HiAP implementation, b) on assessing health impacts of other policies (e.g. diplomas or Master of Public Health)? What education there is?
- Are there specific persons or units with responsibility for taking HiAP further at national level? For example, in Council of state, Ministry of Health or National Public Health Institutes or any other public authority. What are they?

(6) Intersectoral public health policy or strategy

Is there an intersectoral public health policy, strategy, or decision in principle?

The document, any documentation on its preparation, including information on organizations and participants in the preparation, and on monitoring, and review of evaluation is collected.

(7) Finding the laws implementing certain EU directives

To increase the comparability of our study we will also compare the processes of implementing some European level intersectoral policies: we have chosen two EU directives for that, as an EU directive needs to be implemented in national laws and therefore includes some flexibility to do so.¹

We are interested in studying how objectives defined in the directive are met in each country (in other words, what means are used), which sectors/ ministries will participate in the process of defining the means, what kind of path does the transposing of directive follow in each country and is HiAP approach applied in this process and if yes, how?

Check how the following directives have been implemented in national laws. Gather information also on general processes and how health has been considered for and how the ministry of health has been consulted?

a) AV-directive (2018/1808)

Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD) originally ratified in 2010, revision proposed by EU Commission in 2016. Current version successfully revised in 2018, accessed from attached link [[L_2018303EN.01006901.xml \(europa.eu\)](#)]

Let's call it AV-directive. We are interested in that part of the directive that deals with marketing children's food.

b) EIA-directive (2011/92/EU)

Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) directive originally ratified on 13th December 2011, revised 16th April 2014. Current version accessed from attached link [[L_2012026EN.01000101.xml \(europa.eu\)](#)]

[Directive - 2014/52 - EN - EIA - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](#) (From here you can access the directive in your language)

Both chosen directives will provide us with cases to study how EU-policy is implemented nationally and if and how HiAP approach is applied.

¹ What is EU-directive? According to Greer & al. (2019, 42) "EU-directive is EU-legislation that Member States must transpose into their own domestic law. It sets out the objectives to be achieved but leaves it up to member states as to how they achieve those objectives in their national context."

(8) Have we missed something essential?

Are there any other evaluation, reviews or reports articles, which have a focus on HiAP?

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